

1 **Classification of Architectural and MEP BIM Objects for Building Performance** 2 **Evaluation**

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6 **ABSTRACT**

7 Numerous factors in current workflows reduce the completeness, accuracy, and reliability of
8 the information exchanged between Building Information Modelling (BIM) authoring tools and
9 building performance simulation and analysis software. Automated classification of BIM
10 objects could ameliorate most of the interoperability problems. However, architectural,
11 structural, mechanical, electrical, and plumbing (MEP), and other building objects have a wide
12 range of shapes, features, and properties, which makes identifying them reliably and accurately
13 with any single AI tool difficult. This study explored methods and techniques for automated
14 classification of architectural and MEP BIM objects that can significantly reduce or eliminate
15 the manual effort required to correct data exchange and interoperability issues in pre-processing
16 building models for performance evaluation. A series of ensemble models using a stacking
17 mechanism of four classification tools (semantic keyword search, rule-based inferencing,
18 machine learning using object geometry features, and deep learning using visual shape features)
19 were implemented and tested. A BIM object dataset with 3,410 instances belonging to 40
20 classes was compiled for training and testing the models. The dataset contains diverse
21 architecture and MEP objects with high-quality selected instances and is available for public
22 use. We found that an ensemble learning approach that exploits the various types of information
23 available in instance models may exhibit superior object classification performance than any
24 individual tool. The ensemble model applying all four tools achieved 91.0% accuracy (F1 score
25 0.88), suggesting that automated classification using ensemble learning is an effective strategy.

26 *KEYWORDS: Building information model; Building object classification; Building*
27 *performance evaluation; Ensemble learning; Semantic enrichment.*

28 **1. INTRODUCTION**

29 Within the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) sector, the building
30 performance domain encompasses the range of functions that buildings are anticipated to fulfill,
31 including energy efficiency, indoor environmental quality, and thermal and visual comfort (de
32 Wilde, 2019). Many performance analysis and simulation software tools are available for
33 making these assessments during design, and most require explicit geometry definition of a

34 building's structure, space partitioning, furniture, mechanical, electrical, and plumbing (MEP)
35 systems, and so on, with domain-specific parameters that determine their function (e.g., thermal
36 properties of building components, usage and operation schedules, internal loads for lighting
37 and miscellaneous equipment, etc.) (Bazjanac, 2009; Celebi, 1998; Maile et al., 2007). This
38 information is commonly contained in BIM models, but extracting the information and pre-
39 processing it for building performance simulations and analyses is hampered by:

- 40 - Mis-matches between the model schema of BIM modelling software and the native
41 schema of building performance software. Although the building data (e.g., geometry)
42 can be mapped from BIM to native simulation models (de Wilde, 2019), BIM
43 applications and performance simulation software tools have a vendor-specific native
44 schema with different object aggregation, identification, and parametrization, which
45 often results in inaccurate, incomplete, or incorrect mappings (Bloch & Sacks, 2018;
46 Chung & Ashuri, 2022).
- 47 - Inconsistencies introduced by export routines that export data from BIM software to
48 open-standard information exchange formats such as Green Building XML (gbXML)
49 and Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) (Chung & Ashuri, 2022; Sanhudo et al., 2018).
- 50 - Insufficient level of detail of object classification where the lowest level IFC schema
51 class is generic (e.g., *IfcFurniture*) and enumerated values for object type are not set.
- 52 - Classification errors introduced through poor modelling practices (Howard & Björk,
53 2008; Sacks et al., 2018). Misclassification hinders the potential use of BIM models in
54 performance as these tasks depend on accurate object classification (Ma et al., 2018).

55 Automated classification of BIM objects in the data preparation process using semantic
56 enrichment tools could potentially overcome most of these issues (Belsky et al., 2016).
57 Semantic enrichment has been demonstrated for object classification in narrow domains, such
58 as bridge object detection and classification (Ma et al., 2018; Sacks et al., 2016; SeeBridge,
59 2017b, 2017a). Researchers have implemented object classification algorithms on 3D
60 computer-aided design (CAD) model objects mainly using machine learning (ML) or rule-
61 based methods, with almost exclusive focus on the architectural and structural domains (Kim
62 et al., 2019; Koo et al., 2019; Qin et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2015; Wu & Zhang, 2018; Xue et
63 al., 2021).

64 This research aims to contribute insights into methods and techniques for developing classifiers
65 for semantically enriching BIM objects within the field of building performance. Using such a
66 classifier, a design team could process BIM model files to prepare information with
67 classifications that are directly compatible with the schema of target performance analysis
68 applications. The guiding objective is to achieve a high level of classification accuracy, and
69 thus to relieve design teams of the manual effort that is currently necessary to prepare models
70 for analysis tools.

71 The architectural, structural, and MEP objects that are needed for building performance
72 analyses have a wide range of shapes, features, and properties, which makes it difficult to
73 identify them reliably and consistently with any single AI tool. State-of-the-art methods each
74 apply a single technique with some subset of possible features, such as geometry and spatial
75 topology (Sacks et al., 2017; Wu & Zhang, 2018, 2019). Consequently, we implemented and
76 tested an ensemble learning approach that can use multiple tools for classification, applying
77 both symbolic and semantic reasoning and machine learning. The ensemble model (EM) uses
78 a stacking mechanism of four individual classification tools: semantic keyword search (SKS),
79 rule-based inferencing (RBI), machine learning (ML) using object geometry features, and deep
80 learning (DL) using visual shape features. A comprehensive dataset with 3,410 instances
81 belonging to 40 common classes of building objects was compiled to train, validate, and test
82 the model, and to explore the marginal contributions of each of the four constituent tools. The
83 dataset includes diverse feature data for each instance: object semantic properties, domain
84 knowledge on spatial and connection relationships among objects, geometry features, and
85 rendered images that encode object shapes.

86 The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides background on BIM objects
87 in the building performance domain, automated BIM object classification methods, and
88 ensemble learning approaches in the AEC sector. Section 3 describes the aims, scope, and
89 method. Section 4 explains the compilation of the dataset. Section 5 specifies the
90 implementation of the individual tools and the ensemble learning wrapper, including training
91 and validation. Section 6 reports evaluation and results. Section 7 discusses the quality of the
92 dataset and performance of individual tools and ensemble models before the conclusions are
93 presented in Section 8.

94 **2. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK**

95 **2.1. BIM Objects in the Building Performance Domain**

96 In the process of building design, design decisions that incorporate performance targets evolve
97 through a series of feedback loops, involving the collaborative efforts of multidisciplinary
98 design teams (e.g., architects, engineers, and energy specialists) (Gao et al., 2019). The building
99 performance evaluation models encompass: (i) building systems and components, collectively
100 called MEP, including heating, cooling, and ventilation (HVAC) systems, electrical and
101 communication systems, and plumbing systems (Celebi, 1998); (ii) building elements (e.g.,
102 walls, floors, doors, roofs, windows); and (iii) interior design elements (e.g., furnishing objects)
103 (Nasrollahi & Shokri, 2016; Reinhart, 2002). The building elements are used in most building
104 performance valuations, although the attributes required differ for each specific performance
105 function (e.g., electrical, visual, thermal behaviour) (Citherlet, 2001). The shapes and reflective
106 characteristics of furniture pose challenges and increase complexity when assessing lighting

107 impacts on surfaces, especially in the presence of multiple light sources. Each piece of furniture
108 may require different light intensity to suit the associated human activities (Jin & Lee, 2019).

109 To facilitate collaboration among diverse stakeholders throughout various stages of the building
110 lifecycle, BIM provides a digital representation encompassing both the physical and functional
111 attributes of a building. Information within a BIM model can be created, retrieved, modified,
112 and updated to align with each stakeholder (Lam, 2018). Pinheiro et al. (2018) explained the
113 information exchange process from BIM models to building energy performance simulation
114 (BEPS) tools. It starts with architects creating a building geometry model with a BIM authoring
115 tool, which then undergoes space boundary checks. HVAC engineers supplement HVAC system
116 components and parameters to this model ensuring quality through a coherence check
117 employing specific rules with an HVAC Model Checker. Later, energy specialists control the
118 completeness, consistency, and validity of the model containing both architectural and HVAC
119 systems, and they may request additional/missing data from architects and engineers if needed.
120 Lastly, energy specialists enhance the energy performance model to suit the targeted simulation
121 tool. A seamless translation from BIM to BEPS tools hinges on the Model View Definition
122 (MVD)'s inclusion of the necessary subset from the target domain, formatted according to the
123 BIM schema (Pinheiro et al., 2018).

124 Many software vendors have implemented information exchange through open data schema,
125 mainly IFC and gbXML. Although these data schemas encompass data exchange among
126 diverse energy analysis tools, some parameters pertinent to HVAC components are notably
127 absent (Van Treeck et al., 2018). Kamel & Memari (2019) found that the data on loads, thermal
128 zones, and HVAC system (split heat pump) was not transferred from a BIM authoring tool
129 (Revit) to an energy simulation tool (OpenStudio) through gbXML. IFC4, the most recent
130 version, does not support the characterization of all HVAC system components, posing a
131 significant obstacle to communication of the HVAC objects and their information for energy
132 simulation (El Asmi et al., 2015). Furthermore, the schema lacks detail where multiple
133 components are aggregated and represented in a single building object class. For example, heat
134 pumps encompass several components like filters, valves, compressors, condensers,
135 evaporators, sensors, actuators, and control units, and all of these are modelled using
136 *IfcUnitaryEquipment* (Pinheiro et al., 2018).

137 These shortcomings lead some researchers to propose extensions to the IFC schema to meet the
138 requirements of target simulation tools, mainly by using the IDM (Information Delivery
139 Manual)/MVD method. El Asmi et al. (2015) enriched IFC with the HVAC system description
140 according to the COMETH simulation engine. The defined HVAC systems and components in
141 exchange requirements were: mechanical ventilation system (e.g., fan), heating system (e.g.,
142 boiler, cooling tower, pumps), hot water system, and photovoltaic system (e.g., solar device).
143 Pinheiro et al. (2018) implemented the IDM/MVD method for information transfer from IFC-

144 based BIM to BEPS tools (EnergyPlus and Modelica), proposing an IFC extension that adds
145 properties to eight different HVAC components (*IfcBoiler*, *IfcCoil*, *IfcDuctSegment*, *IfcFan*,
146 *IfcPump*, *IfcSpaceHeater*, *IfcController*, and *IfcValve*).

147 Moreover, IFC specifications do not possess the formal rigor needed to unambiguously
148 encapsulate the complete semantics required for seamless and dependable information
149 exchange (Belsky, 2021). Zhang & El-Gohary (2020) proposed a value-specific information
150 extraction method from the IFC-based BIM model to evaluate human comfort (e.g., energy and
151 acoustic) and make human-centered decisions in the design stage. They extracted value-specific
152 information, as semantics, from BIM objects (in the object's name and type, as well as object
153 properties names and nominal values) and extended the IFC4 with new entities (e.g.,
154 *IfcElectricGridElement*) and properties (e.g., noise reduction coefficient). BIM objects and
155 models from diverse disciplines in the AEC industry, with different classification and parameter
156 sets, lead to semantic ambiguity in BIM documents (Gao et al., 2015), which results in
157 challenges for reuse and interoperability (Wu et al., 2019). Present-day information retrieval
158 from BIM object databases predominantly depends on keyword-based search techniques (e.g.,
159 Boolean or probabilistic models) and natural-language-based models (Gao et al., 2015; Wu et
160 al., 2019).

161 A benchmark study by Noardo et al. (2021) involving various IFC software programs and
162 external volunteers reported IFC implementation issues in interoperability. Developing
163 effective solutions for mapping, conversions, and object transformations into other formats is
164 nearly impossible without a stable and reliable initial format as a foundation. The authors
165 underlined the potential bias that may arise from participants' varying levels of expertise or
166 initial inaccuracies in the provided models. However, this bias mirrors how users practically
167 employ software and produce data in real-world usage scenarios.

168 To sum up, the IFC schema is inadequate for a complete and accurate exchange of performance
169 domain information. Consequently, users often need to input this information manually. This
170 requires intensive work, is prone to human error and results in inaccurate simulations (Sanhudo
171 et al., 2018).

172 **2.2. Automated BIM Object Classification**

173 Researchers have developed automated classification approaches to detect and recognize
174 building objects according to their features and attributes (Wu & Zhang, 2018). Most apply a
175 single tool with rule-based, machine-learning or deep-learning methods, while some apply a
176 hybrid approach with multiple tools.

177 Belsky et al. (2016) developed a prototype rule-processing semantic enrichment engine for BIM
178 (SeeBIM). SeeBIM was a forward-chaining IF-THEN rule processing system that used the
179 geometry, spatial topology, and property and relationship information of building object

180 instances. See BIM was used to detect and classify objects in BIM models of highway bridges
181 (Sacks et al., 2016; See Bridge, 2017b, 2017a). Utkucu & Sacks (2023) implemented four rule
182 sets, based on geometry features (e.g., object dimensions) and topological relationships (e.g.,
183 contain, above, below), to classify four MEP BIM object types (Variable air volume terminals
184 (VAV), sound speakers, switches and electric sockets). Although the rule-based classifier
185 achieved at least 90% accuracy, multiple false positives and negatives occurred in the switch
186 and socket classes since the rule sets could not distinguish the geometry and topology features
187 of the objects.

188 Ma et al. (2018) developed a feature-based matching algorithm based on 3D object shape
189 features (e.g., extension, orientation, volume) and pairwise relationships (e.g., touching,
190 overlapping, orthogonality) obtained from domain experts' knowledge to classify bridge
191 objects. The algorithm was implemented on a bridge model containing 59 bridge objects under
192 eight classes, and classified all of them correctly. The authors concluded that a hybrid approach,
193 integrating RBI and ML, might reduce the dependency on domain expert knowledge. However,
194 3D object classification via ML was, and still is, limited by the lack of large datasets of properly
195 labeled BIM models.

196 Wu & Zhang (2018) proposed a rule-based method based on objects' geometry representations
197 for automated BIM object classification and tested it with three bridge pier objects. The authors
198 underlined the need to test more shape categories, which might result in multiple-category
199 matches for an object. In later work, Wu & Zhang (2019) developed a pattern-matching rule-
200 based method built on the IFC objects geometric representation (e.g., swept solid, boundary
201 representation (Brep), constructive solid geometry (CSG)) for five predefined IFC categories
202 (beam, column, footing, slab, and wall) and 11 non-IFC beam type categories (e.g., rectangular
203 and round beams). The proposed method was tested with 1,325 objects in training and 566
204 objects in testing data and achieved 84.5% recall and 85.2% precision for the IFC classes and
205 100% recall and precision for the non-IFC beam classes. The authors emphasized that the main
206 limitation was the development of the algorithm containing all possible geometric
207 representations of the objects, which is labour-intensive.

208 Koo et al. (2019) examined classification of building elements mapped from six architectural
209 BIM models, based on geometry and relational behaviours using support vector machines
210 (SVM). They first tested mapped elements in eight IFC classes and then detected the elements'
211 subtypes within individual IFC classes. The authors concluded that this approach supplies the
212 verification of BIM models with a high level of accuracy and supplements semantics for
213 domain-specific analysis. Wu et al. (2022) used the invariant features of building objects (e.g.,
214 object geometry, location, and metadata) in an ML formulation for BIM object classification in
215 five categories (beam, column, footing, slab, and wall). Their best-performing algorithm
216 achieved a 0.99 F1 measure in the testing data. The authors concluded that ML algorithms using

217 objects' invariant features are an encouraging approach. Koo et al. (2021) classified
218 infrastructure BIM elements using geometric deep learning (GDL) models (multi-view
219 convolutional neural network (MVCNN) and PointNet). They concluded that MVCNN is the
220 best method for classification of infrastructure BIM elements for the purpose of automating the
221 checking of BIM-to-IFC mappings.

222 Collins et al. (2021) implemented a GDL approach to classify IFC objects from 13 IFC classes
223 of structural elements (*IfcWall*, *IfcSlab*, *IfcColumn*, *IfcWindow*, *IfcDoor*, *IfcStair* *IfcRailing*),
224 MEP equipment (*IfcFlowTerminal*, *IfcFlowSegment*, *IfcFlowFitting*,
225 *IfcDistributionControlElement*, *IfcFlowController*), and interior furniture
226 (*IfcFurnishingElement*). They applied a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) on a dataset of
227 3D objects extracted from 22 BIM models, called the BIMGEOM dataset (Collins, 2021). They
228 investigated which objects' local geometry features are relevant for identifying the IFC classes
229 of the objects. The trained model was validated with unseen object samples from the
230 BIMGEOM dataset and achieved up to 85% accuracy. The authors underlined that the network
231 struggled to learn diverse geometric features in a class (e.g., *IfcFurnishingElement* and
232 *IfcFlowTerminal*) and further underlined that a possible solution might be to label objects with
233 more detailed sub-types.

234 Emunds et al. (2021) emphasized the need for extensive and rich datasets in BIM and IFC to
235 support the implementation of ML and DL methods. They developed a benchmark dataset
236 called IFCNetCore with 7,930 objects belonging to 20 IFC classes containing the 2D projection,
237 point cloud, and triangulated mesh data for each object. Subsequently, they used IFCNetCore
238 to evaluate three DL methods (MVCNN, DGCNN, and MeshNet) using object geometry
239 information. Although the highest accuracy was obtained with the MVCNN method (85.5%
240 balanced accuracy and 0.87 F1 score), the authors pointed out that each method has strengths
241 and weaknesses and they make similar mistakes. In further work, Emunds et al. (2022) proposed
242 the 'SparSE-BIM' workflow, a sparse convolution neural network model, to classify IFC
243 objects based on IFC-based geometry. SparSE-BIM was tested on two IFC entity datasets -
244 IFCNetCore (Emunds et al., 2021) and BIMGEOM (Collins, 2021) - and results were compared
245 with the other methods (MVCNN, DGCNN, and MeshNet). SparSE-BIM achieved better
246 accuracy than the compared methods, except MVCNN, and reduced computational
247 requirements at run time. The authors argued that MVCNN has better performance since it
248 captures fine details (Emunds et al., 2022).

249 Graph neural networks (GNNs) have also been used to classify abstract BIM objects (e.g., room
250 type) (Wang et al., 2021, 2022). In this work, the authors compiled BIM models as graphs and
251 validated that GNNs can leverage the features from object relationships to enhance
252 classification performance.

253 Although these state-of-the-art methods enable automated BIM object classification, there are

254 limitations when applying them to classify fine-grained BIM objects in the building
255 performance domain. The prediction accuracy of the RBI method requires identifying sufficient
256 unique feature values across all possible object types and relationships to determine the objects'
257 classes (Bloch & Sacks, 2018). Constructing effective and comprehensive rule sets for a broad
258 set of object types, which is required in the building performance domain, is rather challenging
259 (Utkucu & Sacks, 2023). The main issues for ML and DL methods in BIM object classification
260 are the needs for: (i) a well-balanced dataset with a unique and large quantity of object samples
261 (Emunds et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022) that is distributed evenly per class, and a sufficiently large
262 training dataset (Koo et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2022); and (ii) extracting the most relevant and
263 informative data from diverse raw data (e.g., object geometry, spatial topology, and other
264 relationships) (Bloch & Sacks, 2018). Researchers have developed several open-source datasets
265 for BIM object classification such as IFCNetCore (Emunds et al., 2021) and BIMGEOM
266 (Collins, 2021). However, as Collins (2021) mentioned, the network model can have difficulties
267 coping with diverse geometric variances within a class. Therefore, fine-grained objects with
268 elaborate sub-types might be needed.

269 The literature shows that researchers have focused predominantly on architectural objects when
270 considering semantic enrichment of the physical entities with their subtypes, less on structural
271 objects, with little attention paid to MEP objects (Xue et al., 2021). Thus, there is a lack of BIM
272 object classification research in the MEP domain.

273 **2.3. Ensemble Learning**

274 Ensemble learning is a technique that combines multiple models to make predictions, resulting
275 in more accurate and reliable outcomes than can be achieved with any single model. Its
276 principle involves combining multiple prediction methods using voting mechanisms by
277 employing different ML algorithms on diverse data projections (Dong et al., 2020). Ensemble
278 learning enhances prediction accuracy and robustness by training a variety of models, like
279 decision trees, neural networks, and linear regression, and then integrating their predictions
280 (Sagi & Rokach, 2018). Ensemble learning has been applied in the AEC industry in areas such
281 as prediction of property valuation (Su et al., 2021), construction defect detection (Li & Song,
282 2022), and automatic control of building elements' Level of Geometry (LOG) (Abualdenien &
283 Borrmann, 2022).

284 Su et al. (2021) proposed an integrated system of BIM and ML, using a Genetic algorithm-
285 optimized gradient boosting regression (GA-GBR) ensemble model for property valuation. The
286 model achieved 89.4% R^2 . The authors concluded that the model provided higher estimation
287 accuracy than previous studies on automated valuation models, where the maximum was 87.9%
288 R^2 . Li & Song (2022) proposed an ensemble learning approach to predict steel bridge deck
289 deflection conditions to provide rational and information-based bridge maintenance decisions.
290 Six ensemble learning models (Random Forest, ExtraTree, AdaBoost, GBDT, XGBoost, and

291 LightGBM) were implemented on data from the National Bridge Inventory (NBI) database.
292 The XGBoost model achieved the highest accuracy (95%) and F1 score (0.97) and it was
293 compared with the traditional ML models (KNN with 85% accuracy and SVM with 76%
294 accuracy). The authors concluded that the EM supplied considerable performance
295 improvements over the traditional ML models. Abualdenien & Borrmann (2022) developed two
296 EMs (Random Forest and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)), trained with 16 geometry
297 features, for the automatic control of building elements' levels of geometry (LOG). The authors
298 concluded that the trained EMs achieved an accuracy between 83% and 85% for classifying
299 building elements' LOG.

300 On the other hand, research on BIM object classification via ensemble learning is quite limited.
301 Yu et al. (2023) implemented ensemble learning to classify nine BIM object types (*IfcBeam*,
302 *IfcColumn*, *IfcCovering*, *IfcDoor* (single, double, other), *IfcSlab*, *IfcWall*, and *IfcWindow*). They
303 utilized two classifiers: (i) an MVCNN classifier with multiple images of the objects; and, (ii)
304 a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) classifier using objects' geometric features (e.g., height, width,
305 area, volume) retrieved from the objects' bounding boxes and adjacency relationships among
306 objects derived from 2D XY-plane projections of the bounding boxes. The classifiers'
307 predictions were combined in an EM via a maximum rule-based algebraic combiner comparing
308 maximum softmax probability output. The predicted class accuracy was increased (+5%) via
309 the EM. The authors emphasized that the significance of the proposed approach is the
310 incorporation of the adjacency relations among the BIM objects into the learning process, which
311 differs from the single classifier studies that focus exclusively on an object's geometric features.
312 However, they concluded that using bounding boxes to represent the geometry was insufficient.

313 Although Yu et al. (2023) also proposed an ensemble learning approach for BIM object
314 classification, our approach differs in the following ways: (i) for object geometric features, our
315 approach leverages a significantly more comprehensive set of features (25 features) derived not
316 only from objects' bounding boxes but also precise mesh representations; (ii) we apply a
317 Random Forest ML algorithm instead of computationally expensive neural networks to
318 construct a classifier that uses geometric features; (iii) in addition to geometric features, object
319 adjacency relationships, and visual features encoded in rendered images, we also use object
320 properties for classification; and (iv) our approach selects stacking (a learning-based method)
321 instead of simple voting (a rule-based method) as the ensemble strategy to combine the
322 prediction of each individual classifier.

323 **3. AIMS, SCOPE, AND METHOD**

324 Automatically classified IFC-based architectural and MEP BIM objects can provide precise
325 building performance models for a targeted simulation tool, which reduces the need for
326 extensive manual labour and enhances data exchange and interoperability. Therefore, this study

327 endeavours to automate the classification of architectural and MEP BIM objects, thereby
328 enhancing their semantic enrichment for building performance modelling and simulation. To
329 do that, the study explores semantic enrichment methods and techniques for BIM objects within
330 the field of building performance.

331 The method involved iterative implementation, testing, evaluation, and refinement of four
332 object classification tools and a set of ensemble mechanisms that integrated different
333 combinations of the four tools. The ensemble mechanisms were configured to fulfil a set of
334 experiments designed to identify the optimum combination and the marginal contribution of
335 each tool. Four of the experiments were designed to expose the marginal contributions of each
336 of the four tools – in each, one of the tools was omitted, and the results were compared with the
337 results of the full ensemble model with all four tools.

338 The underlying assumption in developing the ensemble learning experiments was that
339 exploiting all possible data from the instances of the building performance domain objects that
340 we wish to classify (primarily instances of MEP and furniture objects) would yield the best
341 performance. Input models were available in files exported in conformance with the IFC4
342 Addendum 2 data schema (buildingSMART, 2022). The four individual classification tools are
343 as follows:

- 344 • A semantic keyword search (SKS) tool that captures an object instance’s alphanumeric
345 properties (*Entity Class, Name, Description, and Object Type*) from its attributes and
346 class inheritance, as used in Zhang & El-Gohary, 2020). This information provides
347 texts that can be searched for the frequency of occurrence of terms from a predefined
348 set of semantic keywords. Thus, the SKS algorithm queries semantics encapsulated in
349 a set of keywords and builds a classification prediction vector for an object. The
350 method was adapted from that of Micci-Barreca (2001).
- 351 • A rule-based inferencing (RBI) tool that checks spatial topology relationships between
352 instances that express common engineering design knowledge. For example, tables
353 are generally adjacent to floors; pipes are generally connected to other piping system
354 objects. The RBI tool captures two spatial topology relationships: a) adjacency
355 between each candidate instance and the nearest wall, floor, and ceiling as vectors of
356 three binary (true/false) values; and b) connectivity relationships for MEP system
357 components (e.g., piping and duct loops).
- 358 • A machine learning (ML) tool using 25 features computed from triangular meshes
359 generated from each instance’s geometry representation from an IFC file. It captures
360 3D geometry features that are provided in IFC files as either boundary representation
361 meshes or as constructive solid geometry. These are converted to triangular mesh
362 geometry to facilitate computation of representative geometry features, as

363 recommended by Abualdenien & Borrmann (2022).

- 364 • A deep learning (DL) classification tool using 12 2D images rendered from each
365 instance to be classified. The images capture the appearance of an object, i.e., ‘what it
366 looks like’. Unlike the abstractions represented by computationally derived features
367 from a triangular mesh, capturing multiple 2D images from different angles of a 3D
368 object preserves the object's shape details and intrinsic geometry (Yu et al., 2023).

369 **Table 1** lists eight ensemble model experiments (EMs). EM1 incorporated spatial topology
370 relations (adjacency and connection) from the RBI tool. EM2 integrated the SKS and RBI tools,
371 and EM3 integrated the ML and DL tools; comparing their results allows comparison of the
372 rule-based vs. the learning tools. EM4 amalgamated all four classification tools (SKS, RBI, ML,
373 and DL). Following EM4, the individual contributions of each tool were assessed through EM5,
374 EM6, EM7, and EM8, where each omitted one of the tools.

375 *Table 1. The Ensemble Models*

No.	EM	SKS	RBI (Adjacency, Connection)	ML	DL
1	Spatial Topology Only	X	✓	X	X
2	Rule-based Only	✓	✓	X	X
3	Learning-based Only	X	X	✓	✓
4	Full Ensemble Model	✓	✓	✓	✓
5	Without SKS	X	✓	✓	✓
6	Without RBI	✓	X	✓	✓
7	Without ML	✓	✓	X	✓
8	Without DL	✓	✓	✓	X

376 *EM: Ensemble Models; SKS: Semantic Keyword Search, RBI: Rule-based Inferencing, ML: Machine Learning,
377 DL: Deep Learning

378 Four correctness performance evaluation criteria were selected. Accuracy represents the
379 probability of correct model predictions. Precision quantifies the reliability of individual
380 positive predictions. Recall refers to the model's capacity to identify all positive units within
381 the dataset. The F1 score combines Precision and Recall using a harmonic mean. The macro-
382 average method, assigning the same weight in the average per class, was used to compute the
383 F1 scores. In this method, there is no connection to class size because equal weight is assigned
384 to every class, regardless of its size. Detailed definitions of the metrics can be found in Grandini
385 et al. (2020).

386 The last aspect of the method concerned the precision of the results. To check the significance
387 of the differences between the results of different experiments, we implemented 5-fold cross-
388 validation for each model and performed T-tests on the distributions.

389 4. DATASET DEVELOPMENT

390 AI classification tools that use learning require large datasets, and in the case of the
391 classification of BIM objects for building performance analyses, the dataset must have classes
392 that are more fine-grained than those of the IFC schema. No such dataset was available, and
393 therefore, we compiled a large BIM object dataset with diverse feature data for each instance
394 stored in IFC, PLY, and PNG formats. The objects in the dataset are from four building systems
395 (furnishing, mechanical, electrical, and plumbing) that inform the aspects of heating, ventilation
396 and air conditioning, visual quality, acoustic performance, water supply, and fire protection.

397 Since interior systems influence visual comfort (Jin & Lee, 2019), seven furniture object types
398 (bed, cabinet, chair, desk, shelf, sofa, and table) were included in the dataset, considering
399 different human activities (e.g., sleeping, reading, working). We considered two types of HVAC
400 systems for residential and commercial buildings: heating/cooling coil and radiator central
401 heating. The heating/cooling coil ensures the supply air is conditioned to regulate indoor
402 temperature through a VAV box controlling the supply air's temperature. The conditioned air is
403 distributed to designated zones, and exhaust air is removed from the same zones through the
404 duct system. Valves, fans, and pumps control the flow rate of air, water, and refrigerant in the
405 HVAC system (Afram & Janabi-Sharifi, 2014). Therefore, VAV, valve, fan, pump, diffuser,
406 three duct fitting object types (bend, junction, and transition), and two duct segment object
407 types (rectangular and round) were sampled in the dataset. Radiator central heating systems
408 comprise boilers as heat generation sources, pipework serving supply and return water, and
409 radiators that distribute heat within a room (Moftakhari et al., 2017). Thus, our dataset included
410 radiators, four types of pipe fittings (bend, lateral, tee junctions, and transitions), and pipe
411 segments. Notably, the boiler object was omitted from the dataset due to a lack of samples.
412 Together with pipework, toilets, sinks, sprinklers and fire extinguisher objects were included in
413 the dataset, respectively for water supply and usage and fire safety. Electrical system
414 components are utilized for solar and artificial lighting calculations, luminance simulation, and
415 energy analysis (Farooq et al., 2017). Thus, light fixtures, sockets, switches, sensors, alarms
416 and thermostats were sampled. Miscellaneous electric loads, contributing significantly to
417 building energy consumption (Butzbaugh et al., 2021), were represented in the dataset by
418 cooker, refrigerator, television, camera, and speaker objects. Cable tracing network connects
419 the electrical equipment for power system planning with circuit continuity checking (Farooq et
420 al., 2017); thus, cable carrier segment and fitting objects, inside the cable tracing network, were
421 sampled. The sampled alarm, television, and speaker objects are sources of noise that relevant
422 when evaluating acoustic performance.

423 *Figure 1* illustrates the workflow for compiling the BIM object dataset. Two approaches were
424 used to collect objects samples. First, relevant objects were extracted from IFCNetCore, an
425 open-source dataset (Emunds et al., 2021), in IFC, PLY, and image formats. These samples are

426 represented in the IFCNetCore column in **Table 2**. The BIM object dataset has 40 object classes;
427 however, the IFCNetCore dataset does not contain some object classes (e.g., samples under
428 *IfcAudioVisualAppliance*, *IfcElectricAppliance*, and *IfcFireSuppressionTerminal*). Thus, we
429 added additional relevant BIM object samples from open-source BIM object libraries (e.g.,
430 RevitCity (Pierced Media LC, 2023), BIM Object (bimobject, 2023), BIM Store (bimstore,
431 2023), NBS Source (NBS Enterprises Ltd, 2023), and CIC BIM Object Library (Construction
432 Industry Council, 2023)). These samples are collected in the VClab (Virtual Construction
433 Laboratory) column in **Table 2**. The object samples obtained from open-source BIM object
434 libraries were represented as individual objects in family files. BIM models were created
435 containing the objects using Revit as a BIM authoring tool (Autodesk, 2022). Object geometry
436 models (solid geometry as polygon mesh in PLY) for each collected building object in VClab
437 were extracted from an IFC model using IfcOpenShell, (IfcOpenShell, 2022), and Trimesh
438 library (Trimesh, 2022). The object geometry models (PLY) were rendered using the
439 BlenderPhong package (MIT License, 2023). In the algorithm, the camera was located around
440 an object in 12 orientations with a 30-degree elevation; thus, 12 images were rendered of the
441 object. To sum up, three data source formats (IFC, object geometry in PLY, and image) were
442 established for all object samples.

443 Furthermore, the object samples' quality was checked with respect to duplicated and low-
444 quality objects, as defined in (Ying et al., 2023). The duplicated objects exhibit substantial
445 similarity or are identical to other objects (Ying et al., 2023). Objects whose LOD was less than
446 LOD 300 were defined as low-quality. All invalid and low-quality objects were eliminated to
447 improve data quality. Next, we examined each object and determined its ground truth
448 classification. The assigned ground truth label consists of the lowest level IFC entity class name
449 (subclass or sub-subclass in **Table 2**) and the object type. Lastly, the prediction vectors were
450 generated by implementing four individual classifiers over the relevant data sources (IFC, PLY,
451 and image) and stored in CSV format in the BIM object dataset.

452 In total, 4,045 BIM object instances were collected – 1,946 (48%) from IFCNetCore and 2,099
453 (52%) from models in the VCLAB repository. Checks for duplicates and quality checks led to
454 deletion of 635 instances (73 from IFCNetCore and 562 from VCLAB). The resulting dataset
455 contains 3,410 valid BIM object instances with their IFC and PLY geometry files. Twelve
456 images were rendered for each valid object sample, yielding 40,920 images. **Table 2** provides
457 the distribution of the instances over the classes. The BIM object dataset was randomly split
458 into three subsets for training and testing our ensemble learning approach, namely the training
459 subset (70%; 2,410 instances), the validation subset (11%; 364 instances), and the test subset
460 (19%; 636 instances).

461 The retrieved entity class labels and the ground truth labels for all the objects in the dataset
462 were compared to determine to what extent the assumptions made in the introduction section

463 concerning the quality of information held true. Of the 3,410 objects in the dataset, 704 objects
 464 (21%) were listed as *IfcBuildingElementProxy*, which means that they were unclassified. A
 465 further 396 objects (12%) were correctly classified: these belonged to the
 466 *IfcCableCarrierSegment*, *IfcLightFixture*, *IfcCableCarrierFitting*, *IfcAlarm*, *IfcSensor*,
 467 *IfcValve*, and *IfcPump* classes. Some 2,226 objects (65%) were classified with 14 entity classes
 468 from the IFC schema that do not provide sufficient detail of the object for running building
 469 performance simulations and analyses. These are *IfcAirTerminal*, *IfcDuctFitting*,
 470 *IfcDuctSegment*, *IfcFireSuppressionTerminal*, *IfcFlowController*, *IfcFlowFitting*,
 471 *IfcFlowSegment*, *IfcFlowTerminal*, *IfcFurnishingElement*, *IfcFurniture*, *IfcOutlet*,
 472 *IfcPipeFitting*, *IfcSpaceHeater*, and *IfcUnitaryControlElement*. Finally, 84 objects (2%) were
 473 found to be mislabelled. For instance, six thermostats, two pumps, and a sensor had the
 474 *IfcFlowTerminal* entity class. In the dataset, therefore, only 12% of the object classifications
 475 were found to be useful for performance analysis. The remaining objects exhibited an
 476 inadequate level of detail within their respective object classes. In the normal process of
 477 engineering design, this is a significant limitation, and it highlights poor modelling practices
 478 and an insufficient level of detail in object classification.

479

480
 481 Note: IFCGUID is the globally unique ID for objects recorded in IFC files. UUID is a universal unique ID derived
 482 from the IFCGUID to associate each object's 3D geometry and images files.

483 Figure 1. The Dataset Construction Workflow.

484

485

486 Table 2. BIM Object Dataset According to Ground Truth Classifications

Level 1 (Class)	Level 2 (Subclass)	Level 3 (Sub-subclass)	Level 4 (Object Type)	Number of Objects			Number of Invalid Objects	Number of Valid Objects	Number of Images
				IFCNetCore	VClab	Total			
<i>IfcFurnishingElement</i>	<i>IfcFurniture</i>	-	Bed	0	95	95	23	72	864
			Cabinet	38	69	107	8	99	1,188
			Chair	21	68	89	8	81	972
			Desk	0	141	141	38	103	1,236
			Shelf	0	105	105	19	86	1,032
			Sofa	0	116	116	30	86	1,032
			Table	0	104	104	3	101	1,212
<i>IfcDistributionControlElement</i>	<i>IfcAlarm</i>	-	Alarm	0	61	61	24	37	444
	<i>IfcSensor</i>	-	Sensor	0	106	106	37	69	828
	<i>IfcUnitaryControlElement</i>	-	Thermostat	0	100	100	59	41	492
<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowController</i>	<i>IfcAirTerminalBox</i>	Variable Air Volume (VAV)	0	97	97	36	61	732
		<i>IfcSwitchingDevice</i>	Switch	5	71	76	21	55	660
		<i>IfcValve</i>	Valve	168	0	168	4	164	1,968
	<i>IfcFlowFitting</i>	<i>IfcCableCarrierFitting</i>	Cable Carrier Fitting	161	0	161	11	150	1,800
		<i>IfcDuctFitting</i>	Bend	144	0	144	3	141	1,692
			Junction	89	0	89	0	89	1,068
			Transition	179	0	179	0	179	2,148
		<i>IfcPipeFitting</i>	Bend	185	0	185	0	185	2,220
			Junction (Lateral)	57	54	111	25	86	1,032
	Junction (Tee)		98	0	98	1	97	1,164	
	<i>IfcFlowMovingDevice</i>	<i>IfcFan</i>	Fan	0	85	85	14	71	852
		<i>IfcPump</i>	Pump	0	105	105	4	101	1,212
<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowSegment</i>	<i>IfcCableCarrierSegment</i>	Cable Carrier Segment	118	0	118	1	117	1,404
		<i>IfcDuctSegment</i>	Rectangular	138	0	138	18	120	1,440
		Round	140	0	140	16	124	1,488	
	<i>IfcPipeSegment</i>	Pipe Segment	144	0	144	1	143	1,716	
	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcAirTerminal</i>	Diffuser	72	33	105	2	103	1,236
		<i>IfcAudioVisualAppliance</i>	Camera	0	31	31	16	15	180
			Speaker	0	75	75	34	41	492
		<i>IfcElectricAppliance</i>	Television (TV)	0	50	50	12	38	456
			Cooker	0	36	36	21	15	180
		Refrigerator	0	32	32	17	15	180	
<i>IfcFireSuppressionTerminal</i>		Fire Extinguisher	0	27	27	11	16	192	
Sprinkler	0	22	22	5	17	204			
<i>IfcLightFixture</i>	Light Fixture	29	68	97	15	82	984		
<i>IfcOutlet</i>	Socket	0	85	85	22	63	756		
<i>IfcSanitaryTerminal</i>	Sink	48	61	109	32	77	924		
	Toilet	49	51	100	8	92	1,104		
<i>IfcSpaceHeater</i>	Radiator	35	67	102	10	92	1,104		
SUMMARY				1,946	2,099	4,045	635	3,410	40,920

488 **5. IMPLEMENTATION**

489 In this study, we utilized diverse object features presented in various formats from four
 490 classification tools: SKS for object semantic properties, RBI for topological relationships
 491 among objects (adjacency and connection relations), ML for object geometry features (e.g.,
 492 edges, faces, dimensions, etc.), and DL for object shapes captured in 2D rendered images. These
 493 feature sets were harnessed within an ensemble learning approach.

494 **5.1. Tool 1: Semantic Keyword Search (SKS)**

495 The SKS algorithm extracts the object’s alphanumeric properties (*Entity class*, *Name*,
 496 *Description*, and *ObjectType*) from IFC-based BIM models using IfcOpenShell (IfcOpenShell,
 497 2022) and concatenates them in a text string with all capitals, denoted T . The algorithm then
 498 searches T for occurrences of each keyword $K_{i,j}$ in the keyword set M_i for each class i
 499 corresponding to the object classes. The keyword sets include keywords derived from the IFC
 500 schema, the class name itself, and additional semantic terms. **Table 3** illustrates this. In each
 501 row, the first keywords are derived from the three levels of class names (in italics) and the class
 502 name itself. The latter keywords, shown in italics, are additional semantic terms added by the
 503 authors. The full set of keywords is provided in **Appendix A**. The frequency f_i is a count of the
 504 total number of times that any of the keywords $K_{i,j}$ appear in the concatenated text T .

505 *Table 3. Three examples of keyword sets for object classes.*

Class No.	Class hierarchy from the IFC schema			Class Name	Keyword Set
7	<i>IfcFurnishingElement</i>	<i>IfcFurniture</i>	-	Table	{FURNISHING, FURNITURE, TABLE, KITCHEN, DINING}
27	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcOutlet</i>	Socket	{FLOW, TERMINAL, OUTLET, SOCKET, PLUG, ELECTRIC}
35	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcSanitaryTerminal</i>	Toilet	{FLOW, TERMINAL, SANITARY, TOILET, BATHROOM, WC, SEWAGE}

506 The prediction vector was calculated based on the transformation of individual values in
 507 categorical independent traits to the probability of the dependent trait (Micci-Barreca, 2001).
 508 Thus, the prediction vector for each candidate instance was calculated by normalising the set
 509 of frequency values between 0 and 1, to represent the probability (p_i) of classification of the
 510 instance as any class i as shown in Eq. (1).

$$p_i = \begin{cases} \frac{f_i}{\sum_{k=1}^N f_k}, & \text{if } \sum_{k=1}^N f_k \neq 0 \\ \frac{1}{N}, & \text{if } \sum_{k=1}^N f_k = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

512 where N is the number of object classes ($N = 40$ in the dataset), and k an integer index
513 ranging from 1 to N .

514 As an example, the calculation of the prediction vector for a particular instance is explained.
515 The keywords in the keyword sets (**Appendix A**) were searched for in the concatenated string
516 “IFCUNITARYCONTROLELEMENTRESIDEO_THERMOSTAT_T4:T4H110A1021:37731
517 4NONERESIDEO_THERMOSTAT_T4:T4H110A1021”. The resulting matrix of N vectors of
518 keyword counts is $[[0,0,0],[0,0,0],[0,0,0,0],[0,0,0],[0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0],$
519 $[0,1,0,0,0,0],[1,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,$
520 $0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,$
521 $0,0],[0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,$
522 $0,0],[0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0,0],[1,0],[0,0,0,0,0],[0,1,0],[1,1,2],[0,1,0,0]]$.

523 The total $\sum f_k$ is nine. Thus, using $\frac{f_i}{\sum_{k=1}^N f_k}$ to calculate the probability for each class yields
524 the prediction vector:

525 $[0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0.11,0.11,0.11,0,0.11,0.44,0.11]$.

526 In cases where none of the keywords are found in the concatenated text, $f_k = 0$ and we assume
527 equal probability for the instance to belong to any of the classes. The elements of the prediction
528 vector are all assigned the value $1/N$ (0.025).

529 The SKS algorithm was applied to the 3,410 instances in the dataset. All 3,410 object instances
530 had valid *Entity class* values, but some had no information in their *Name* (12 objects),
531 *Description* (3,405 objects) and *ObjectType* (18 objects) fields. The content of the *Description*
532 property, in particular, is strongly dependent on the users’ practice. In 131 instances, none of
533 the keywords in the keyword sets corresponding to the object classes were found.

534 The contribution of the keyword search algorithm to classification of BIM objects was
535 investigated in ensemble models (Section 5.5) for enhancing the overall object features. To
536 prepare the input for downstream ensemble learning, an N -length vector is generated for each
537 instance.

538 **5.2. Tool 2: Rule-Based Inference (RBI)**

539 The RBI tool examines two spatial relations among the BIM objects; a geometry computation

540 algorithm for adjacency and a query algorithm for retrieving connection information from IFC-
541 based BIM models. The information processed from these two algorithms was used to assign a
542 unique value for each BIM object to classify objects in light of architectural/engineering design
543 knowledge.

544 Topology relationships represent design abstractions and serve as a foundation for formalizing
545 architectural/engineering design (Rosen & Peters, 1996). In architectural design, this process
546 involves the synthesis of spaces by combining physical elements (e.g., slabs, columns, walls,
547 and furniture) (Akiner, 1986). In MEP systems design, ensuring the location and routing of
548 building system components within spaces requires avoiding conflicts with architectural and
549 structural constraints and adhering to various design criteria (Korman et al., 2003). When
550 objects in an MEP system are topologically connected (e.g., equipment or terminal), they are
551 invariably physically linked to each other through elements (e.g., pipe fittings or segments)
552 (Xiao et al., 2019).

553 The adjacency relation examines whether a BIM object is adjacent to any of three architectural
554 elements that define a space (wall, floor, and ceiling). The result for any given instance is a set
555 of three Boolean values. For example, an instance that is adjacent to the wall and floor but not
556 to any ceiling would have ‘TTF’. There are eight possible situations: *TTT*, *FFF*, *FTT*, *TFE*, *TFT*,
557 *FTF*, *TFF*, and *FFT*. The likelihood of each of these conditions for any given BIM object class
558 reflects the way in which objects are commonly used in buildings. For example, tables, chairs,
559 beds, and other furniture objects will have TTF or FTF, because they rest on a floor, are not
560 adjacent to the ceiling, and may or may not be along a wall. Similarly, a bathroom sink will
561 almost always have TFF as it is typically mounted on a wall. Thus, a set of probability values
562 for each condition can be set for each class according to common or expert knowledge. The
563 adjacency features distributed over the dataset were: 1,044 objects (30.6%) in TTF; 497 objects
564 (14.6%) in TFF; 485 objects (14.2%) in FFT; 473 objects (13.9%) in FFF; 470 objects (13.8%)
565 in TFT; 429 objects (12.6%) in FTF; and 12 objects (0.4%) in FTT. For the bed class, the values
566 were set as [0,0,0,0.1,0,0,0.9,0] (90% of beds are on the floor and adjacent to a wall, 10% on
567 the floor at a distance from a wall). This forms a knowledge matrix that can be used to determine
568 the probability of any BIM object instance belonging to any class *i* according to its actual
569 adjacency triplet value. The eight prediction vectors for adjacency relations for the 40 classes
570 in the dataset are shown in **Appendix B**. In application, the triplet is computed using geometry
571 functions from the Trimesh library (Trimesh, 2022) to determine adjacency of each object
572 instance to the floors, walls, or ceilings in the building. Hence, one can compute the vector of
573 probable association with any object class.

574 The connection relationship was examined through the connection point defining the
575 established physical connections among the BIM objects. The connection relationships between

576 pairs or groups of object instances are defined in IFC via *IfcDistributionPort*, which associates
577 the connected port by *IfcRelConnectsPort* and any connected equipment by
578 *IfRelConnectPortToElement* (Xiao et al., 2019). Additionally, *IfcRelNests* is used to describe a
579 series of *IfcDistributionPort*'s nested within an *IfcDistributionElement* as a special type of
580 decomposition (buildingSMART, 2023). Thus, the query algorithm in the RBI tool extracted
581 connection information of the BIM objects, regarding *IfcRelNests* and *IfcDistributionPort*,
582 from IFC-based BIM models using *IfcOpenShell*, (*IfcOpenShell*, 2022). Four conditions for
583 the number of connection points an object may have were considered: zero, one, two, or more
584 than two connection points. For instance, a pipe segment is likely to have two connection points;
585 a diffuser is likely to have one connection point (0.80 occurrence frequency), two connection
586 points (0.15 occurrence frequency), or more than two connection points (0.05 occurrence
587 frequency). In the dataset, 1,467 objects (43%) had two connection points; 819 objects (24%)
588 had no connection points; 610 objects (17.9%) had one connection point; and 514 objects
589 (15.1%) had more than two connection points.

590 The prediction vectors for the $M=4$ possible connection relationships are shown in *Appendix*
591 *B*. Their values were calculated using Eq. (2):

$$592 \quad p_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^M v_{ij}}{M} \quad (2)$$

593 where p_i is the prediction probability of class i , M is the number of possible observed
594 conditions (four in this case), and v_{ij} is the individual probability of an object of class i
595 having the connection port condition j . When this RBI tool is applied, the number of
596 connection points of an instance is derived from the IFC file, and the associated classification
597 vector is simply read from the set of four vectors in *Appendix B*.

598 **5.3. Tool 3: Machine Learning Using Geometry Features (ML)**

599 Machine learning algorithms have demonstrated remarkable accuracy in predicting common
600 BIM architectural objects (Koo et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2022). We tested several ML models for
601 the best performance, including support vector classifier (SVC), k-nearest neighbours (KNN),
602 Gaussian models, linear support vector classifier, decision tree, and random forest. Twenty-five
603 features were considered, including dimension, location, mesh, and topology features, as shown
604 in *Table 4*, where some features are adopted from Wang et al. (2024).

605 To compute location features, we moved the centroid of each object to the origin to ensure that
606 the location features were measured under the same conditions. Seven mesh-related features
607 were used to compute characteristics from the scale of vertices, edges, faces, and facets. Four
608 topology features were used. The Euler characteristic describes a topological space's shape or
609 structure regardless of how it is bent. Since shapes vary between architectural and MEP

610 domains, this feature could help distinguish object classes. Genus, a topology parameter, gives
 611 the number of holes in a surface (de Saint-Gervais, 2016). Average degree, the average number
 612 of edges per node in a graph, was also considered, by converting the mesh geometry into a
 613 graph to compute this value.

614 *Table 4. Features Used in Machine Learning.*

No.	Category	Feature	Note
1		Area	
2		Volume	
3		Bounding box length	
4	Dimension	Bounding box width	
5		Bounding box height	
6		Ratio of bounding box height and length	
7		Ratio of bounding box height and width	
8		Ratio of bounding box width and length	
9		Maximum in X dimension	
10		Maximum in Y dimension	
11	Location*	Maximum in Z dimension	
12		Minimum in X dimension	
13		Minimum in Y dimension	
14		Minimum in Z dimension	
15		Number of faces	
16		Maximum area of one face	
17		Number of adjacent faces	
18	Mesh	Number of facets	Faces form facets
19		Number of unique edges	
20		Length of unique edges	
21		Number of vertices	
22		Euler characteristic	Describe the object's shape
23	Topology	Genus	Number of holes
24		Average degree	Average connected edges
25		Number connected components	

* Moving the object centroid to the origin

615 5-fold cross-validation was adopted which was detailed in Section 6 to reveal the performance
 616 distribution of models. According to the ML results listed in **Table 5**, the random forest model,
 617 with the highest accuracy of 75.9% on the test dataset, was selected as the machine learning
 618 tool for ensemble learning. One of the inherent strengths of the decision tree algorithm is its

619 ability to automatically select relevant features, eliminating the need for manual feature filtering.
 620 Similarly, the random forest algorithm, a collection of decision trees, inherently possesses this
 621 capability of automatic feature selection to ensure that only the most impactful features are used.

622 *Table 5. Accuracies of the selected ML models*

Tested ML Model	Cross-validation Accuracy	Prediction Accuracy
Support Vector Classifier (SVC)	11.1%	10.1%
K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN)	45.3%	48.7%
Gaussian	30.0%	26.3%
Linear Support Vector Classifier	17.9%	17.1%
Decision Tree	62.5%	66.2%
Random Forest	76.2%	75.9%

623 **5.4. Tool 4: Deep Learning Using Visual Features (DL)**

624 Unlike traditional ML methods that require handcrafted features, DL algorithms automatically
 625 learn useful features directly from the raw data (Lecun et al., 2015). Therefore, in addition to
 626 the ML tool, we included a DL tool in our ensemble learning approach, as it may learn and
 627 exploit useful features that are missing from the features defined for the ML tool.

628 We selected MVCNN for two reasons. First, MVCNN has been shown experimentally to
 629 achieve higher accuracy than the other three types of DL models (i.e., point-based, mesh-based,
 630 and graph-based models) in the BIM object classification task on variable-scale datasets
 631 (Emunds et al., 2021, 2022; Koo et al., 2021). Second, because these three types of DL models
 632 employ geometric learning methods, their learned features might exhibit significant
 633 resemblance to the geometric features tailored for the ML tool. In contrast, MVCNN utilizes
 634 visual features that differ from those geometric features. According to the principle of ensemble
 635 learning, individual models with greater diversity generally yield better overall results.

636 MVCNN’s architecture consists of three parts (Su et al., 2015). The first part (denoted CNN1)
 637 aims to extract view-based features from each of a 3D object’s multi-view images separately.
 638 All the image processing branches share the same parameters in CNN1. Then, the features of
 639 all the images are aggregated at a view-pooling layer using element-wise maximum operation.
 640 These aggregated features are further passed through the last part (denoted CNN2) to obtain a
 641 compact shape descriptor.

642 We captured 12 views of each BIM object for classification. For CNN1, we used ResNet-101
 643 (He et al., 2016) pre-trained on ImageNet (Deng et al., 2009) as the feature extractor network,
 644 instead of VGGs (Simonyan & Zisserman, 2014) that were used in the original MVCNN, as
 645 the experiments on our dataset showed that ResNet-101 surpasses VGGs significantly. A fully

646 connected layer was used for CNN2. The MVCNN model was trained on a desktop with an
647 NVIDIA RTX 3060 GPU with 12 GB memory. We set the batch size of 6 objects ($6 \times 12 = 72$
648 images), a learning rate of 0.00005, and Adam as the optimizer with a weight decay of 0.001.

649 The MVCNN model achieved 88.9% accuracy and 0.86 F1 score on the dataset constructed in
650 Section 4, under the setting of a 5-fold cross validation, which is detailed later in Section 6. The
651 most significant confusion was in distinguishing *IfcDuctSegment_Round* and *IfcPipeSegment*
652 objects. For instance, on the third-fold test dataset, eight *IfcDuctSegment_Round* objects were
653 classified as *IfcPipeSegment* objects; contrarily, three *IfcPipeSegment* objects were classified
654 as *IfcDuctSegment_Round* objects.

655 **5.5. Ensemble learning models**

656 Here, the four developed individual tools are assembled to form a more accurate and robust
657 classifier. The reason behind this is that each individual tool can only make use of partial BIM
658 objects' features for inference, while combining all the individual tools provides an efficient
659 means to leverage all the useful features.

660 An ensemble classification model consists of two essential parts: a set of individual learners
661 and a combination strategy. Ensemble learning models can be roughly categorized into three
662 types: bagging, boosting, and stacking (Zhou, 2021). Bagging involves partitioning the original
663 training set into several non-overlapped subsets and using each subset to train an individual
664 learner (Breiman, 1996). Boosting algorithms start with training an individual learner and then
665 adjust the distribution of the training samples according to the result of the individual learner
666 such that incorrectly classified samples will receive more attention from subsequent individual
667 learners (Zhou, 2021). Both Bagging and Boosting algorithms often utilize homogeneous
668 individual learners, which restrains the training samples to be homogeneous, and voting
669 methods (e.g., majority voting, plurality voting, and weighted voting) for result combination
670 (Zhou, 2021).

671 Stacking differs in two key aspects. First, stacking accommodates heterogeneous individual
672 learners, making it suitable for processing training samples with diverse data types (e.g., images,
673 semantics, and numerical data (Zhou, 2021). Second, stacking combines individual learners
674 using a meta-learner instead of deterministic algorithms (Wolpert, 1992). More specifically,
675 stacking algorithms start by training the first-level learners (i.e., individual learners) using the
676 original training set and then using the outputs of the first-level learners to train a second-level
677 learner (i.e., the meta-learner). Indeed, stacking enables meta-learners that combine multiple
678 models in a cascade system that uses the predictions from the first-tier classifiers as input to
679 train second-tier classifiers (Sewell, 2008; Yu et al., 2023).

680 In the context of this study, the dataset developed in Section 4 comprises features in multiple

681 types, including rendering images, semantic properties, numerical geometry features, and
 682 spatial features. Thus, the stacking mechanism is well-suited to combine the four developed
 683 individual tools, each designed to handle different types of features. For the meta-learner, we
 684 opted for the widely-used multinomial logistic regression, also known as Softmax regression
 685 (Goodfellow et al., 2016), over more complex neural networks to mitigate the risk of overfitting
 686 and reduce computation costs. The scikit-learn python package (Pedregosa et al., 2011) was
 687 leveraged to implement the Softmax regression layer in our ensemble approach.

688 The workflow of our established stacking ensemble approach (**Figure 2**) for classifying an
 689 object instance is as follows. First, the semantic properties, topological and connection
 690 relationships, geometry features, and rendering images of the object instance are processed by
 691 the four developed individual tools including SKS, RBI, ML, and DL, respectively. Each of the
 692 SKS, ML and DL tools generates an N -length probability vector, where N is the number of
 693 classes considered ($N = 40$ in our dataset). The RBI tool produces two N -length prediction
 694 vectors, one from adjacency relationships and the other from connection relationships. The
 695 generated prediction vectors are denoted “P” in **Figure 2**. Subsequently, these vectors are
 696 concatenated according to the designed EMs, serving as the input to the trained SoftMax layer,
 697 ultimately producing the final classification, denoted “R” in **Figure 2**. The concatenated
 698 prediction vectors for each EM were respectively: P2 for EM1; P1 and P2 for EM2; P3 and P4
 699 for EM3; all prediction vectors for EM4; P2, P3, and P4 for EM5; P1, P3, and P4 for EM6; P1,
 700 P2, and P4 for EM7; lastly, P1, P2, and P3 for EM8. Thus, the input vector sizes of the ensemble
 701 layer of the eight EMs are 80, 120, 80, 200, 160, 160, 160, and 160, respectively.

702

703 *Note: Prediction vectors P1, P3, and P4 have 40 elements. P2 has 80 elements.*

704

Figure 2. The Ensemble Learning Approach

705 6. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

706 The eight EMs detailed in **Table 1** were developed to test different combinations of the four
 707 individual tools in the ensemble learning pipeline. **Table 6** lists the averaged prediction accuracy,
 708 precision, recall, and F1 score results for those models. As can be seen, EM4, which integrated
 709 all four tools, achieved the best overall performances.

710 *Table 6. Average Prediction Results*

Tag	Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
ML	Random Forest	78.5%	79.1%	74.0%	0.75
DL	MVCNN	88.9%	89.2%	85.2%	0.86
EM1	Spatial Topology Only	25.7%	16.0%	20.4%	0.14
EM2	Rule-based Only	70.0%	72.9%	67.3%	0.67
EM3	Learning-based Only	90.0%	90.8%	86.1%	0.87
EM4	Full Ensemble Model	91.0%	91.8%	87.3%	0.88
EM5	Without SKS	90.1%	90.9%	86.3%	0.87
EM6	Without RBI	90.9%	91.8%	87.2%	0.88
EM7	Without ML	89.9%	90.5%	86.1%	0.87
EM8	Without DL	86.6%	88.4%	83.7%	0.85

711

712 To determine the level of confidence in the comparisons of these models, a 5-fold cross
713 validation was implemented. The entire dataset was divided randomly into five equal-sized
714 folds, each with 682 samples. The ML and the DL tools and all eight EMs were each trained
715 separately five times, each time using a different combination of four folds, with the remaining
716 fold used for testing. This yielded five sets of results for each of the ML, DL and EMs. The
717 results for the ML and DL tools and EM4 and EM6 were further compared using a paired T test
718 for each of the indicators. *Table 7* shows the T-test results of the four models. The commonly
719 accepted threshold for confidence to establish a difference between two samples in this test is
720 0.05. According to the results in *Table 7*, the results for EM4 and EM6 are significantly different
721 to the results for the ML and DL models, and they are significantly different to one another.

722 *Table 7. Prediction Results for five folds and T Test scores*

Tag	Fold	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
ML	1	79.5%	80.9%	77.6%	0.78
	2	79.3%	77.6%	74.9%	0.75
	3	79.0%	78.8%	73.7%	0.74
	4	78.3%	80.7%	72.9%	0.73
	5	76.5%	77.6%	70.7%	0.72
DL	1	91.6%	92.0%	89.0%	0.89
	2	89.9%	90.7%	87.9%	0.88
	3	90.2%	87.7%	85.0%	0.86
	4	87.4%	88.3%	83.5%	0.85

	5	85.5%	87.1%	80.5%	0.82
EM6 (Without RBI)	1	92.5%	92.7%	90.0%	0.90
	2	91.3%	92.6%	89.3%	0.90
	3	91.6%	90.7%	87.1%	0.88
	4	90.0%	91.5%	85.5%	0.87
	5	88.1%	90.2%	83.3%	0.85
EM4 (Full ensemble model)	1	92.8%	93.1%	90.2%	0.91
	2	91.5%	92.7%	89.4%	0.90
	3	91.8%	90.9%	87.2%	0.88
	4	90.5%	91.8%	86.1%	0.88
	5	88.4%	90.5%	83.7%	0.85
T Test DL – EM6		0.007	0.008	0.004	0.006
T Test DL – EM4		0.006	0.005	0.004	0.005
T Test EM6 – EM4		0.009	0.003	0.042	0.012

723 EM1 and EM2 were designed to test the performance of non-learning-based tools. EM1,
724 combining adjacency and connection relations, had the lowest prediction accuracy (25.7%).
725 This is expected for two reasons. First, many objects had the same adjacency and connection
726 features: 1,044 objects have *TTF* (30.6% of the total sample) and 1,467 objects have two
727 connection ports (43% of the total sample). Second, the prediction vectors for adjacency and
728 connection relations do not have a unique value for each class. EM2, which integrates SKS and
729 RBI, increased prediction accuracy to 70.0%. The contribution of semantic features to the
730 prediction accuracy is approximately 45.3%.

731 EM3, which combines ML and DL, achieved prediction accuracy of 90.0%, which is greater
732 than the individual ML (78.5%), DL (88.9%) and the rule-based EM2 (70%) models. The main
733 confusion in the DL model resulted from a failure to distinguish *IfcDuctSegment_Round* and
734 *IfcPipeSegment* classes. The reason for this confusion is that the visual features of some samples
735 belonging to these two classes are the same, which refers to the weakness of the DL tool. This
736 was mitigated slightly through the combined use of machine learning and deep learning tools
737 in EM3, resulting in a +1.1% improvement of the prediction accuracy measure.

738 Similarly, although EM4 had the best prediction performance (91%), the main confusion was
739 in identifying round duct segments (in *IfcDuctSegment_Round* class) and pipe segments (in
740 *IfcPipeSegment* class). As seen in **Figure 3**, in the third-fold test dataset, eight round duct
741 segment objects were incorrectly classified as pipe segment objects, while four pipe segment
742 objects were classified as round duct segments. **Figure 4** shows images of the round duct
743 segment and pipe segment in the third-fold test dataset. Some of these objects have similar
744 geometric features (e.g., the same diameter, length, and even positioning) and thus have similar

745 visual shapes. As a consequence, distinguishing these objects without any semantic information
746 is difficult, even for practitioners.

747 The marginal contribution of each tool was assessed by comparing the results of four pairs of
748 experiments: EM4 to EM5, EM4 to EM6, EM4 to EM7, and EM4 to EM8. The marginal
749 contribution of the SKS tool was relatively small, as can be seen by comparing EM4 and EM5.
750 Supplementing the semantic properties from SKS with objects' topology relationships,
751 geometry, and visual features enhanced the prediction accuracy by +0.9%. A possible reason
752 for this relatively small contribution is that in the five test datasets, on average, 65% of the
753 objects were under-classified, which refers to a generic and insufficient level of detail in object
754 classification. Most of these were instances in which the classifications in the object labels were
755 limited to the second-level subclass (Level 2 as presented in **Table 2**). Classifications such as
756 *IfcFlowFitting*, *IfcFlowSegment*, *IfcFlowTerminal*, and *IfcFurniture* are insufficiently detailed
757 for most performance analyses. A further 21% of the objects had no labels at all, and some 3%
758 had the wrong labels. This reveals a weakness in the SKS tool, but it also confirms the original
759 problem that motivates this research – labelling of object instances in BIM models is often
760 inconsistent and unreliable.

761 The marginal contribution of the RBI tool, incorporating both adjacency and connection
762 relationships, on the EM model was negligible (+0.1%). The weak contribution of the RBI tool
763 may be attributed in part to the fact that the ML tool already considers object topology features
764 such as the number of possible connections. In more general terms, the problem is that the rule-
765 based feature sets do not yield unique combinations of possible values for any of the classes,
766 which means that by definition they cannot achieve good classification results. Indeed, if a rule-
767 based system had unique feature value combinations for every class, it would be a perfect
768 classifier.

769 The contributions of ML and DL tools to the EM model (comparing EM4 to EM7 and EM8
770 respectively), were +1.1% and +4.4%. respectively Thus, among the four individual tools, the
771 DL tool had the greatest marginal contribution.

772
773 *Figure 3. The Confusion Matrix of EM4 on Third-fold Test Dataset*

774
775 *Figure 4. Examples of image sets used for MVCNN: (a) Round Duct Segment; (b) Pipe*
776 *Segment*

777 **7. DISCUSSION**

778 The overall objective of this research was to learn to classify BIM objects that are needed in
779 building performance models and for running performance analyses at the design and
780 development stages. To this end, we developed and tested various individual tools and ensemble
781 learning models that incorporated the tools. Here, we identify the insights garnered from this

782 study, with a particular emphasis on the dataset quality and the performance of the devised tools,
783 encompassing learning models, algorithmic rule-based models, and combinations of them.

784 **7.1. Quality of the Dataset**

785 Although researchers have developed several open-source datasets for BIM object
786 classification, such as IFCNetCore (Emunds et al., 2021) and BIMGEOM (Collins, 2021), there
787 are no datasets that offer comprehensive object classification with elaboration of sub-types in
788 the performance domain. This necessitated compilation of the BIM object dataset described
789 here. The 40 fine-grained object classes listed in *Table 2* were identified as essential for
790 addressing various performance dimensions such as energy efficiency, visual quality, acoustics,
791 water supply, and fire protection.

792 We considered two issues in the process of data collection and preparation: objects' level of
793 development (LOD) regarding geometry and information and sample size. Objects with LOD
794 less than 300 had insufficient semantic information, geometry, and visual shape features for
795 differentiation. On the other hand, designers (e.g., architects and engineers) often insert objects
796 with LOD 400 or 450, which provide rich semantic properties in their description and
797 documentation, precise geometry features in object models, and sharp shape features in their
798 visual data. The results obtained with such objects aligned with the conclusions of earlier work
799 (e.g. Collins, 2021), which found that classification tools cannot exploit these rich features if
800 the target class hierarchy is not sufficiently fine-grained. However, the more target classes
801 defined, the greater the challenge to find sufficient data objects for each class. For example,
802 while gathering object samples for *IfcFurniture_Shelf* class, we excluded residential decorative
803 shelf objects with high LOD, due to high variation of geometry and insufficient sample size.
804 As a result, the dataset was limited to BIM objects with LOD from 300 to 400. Of 4,045 BIM
805 object instances collected, 3,410 were retained in the dataset.

806 **7.2. Individual Tool Performance**

807 The devised ensemble learning approach for automated BIM object classification in the
808 building performance domain used four individual classification tools (SKS, RBI, ML, and DL),
809 applying symbolic and semantic reasoning and machine learning.

810 The effectiveness of the SKS tool depends on the values of the semantic properties of the objects.
811 The SKS algorithm found thorough semantic properties in only 35% of the object samples in
812 the dataset and produced a unique prediction vector for these objects. For all others,
813 classification probabilities were distributed across multiple classes, and in some, were
814 uniformly distributed by default due to lack of keyword matches. The inconsistency and
815 frequent absence of keywords in IFC models is a strong limitation on performance of this tool,
816 and it cannot be used in isolation.

817 The adjacency and connection rules used in the RBI tool were compiled on the basis of
818 engineering design knowledge of the objects' relationships. To generate unique classifications,
819 an RBI tool must have some unique combination of feature values for every object class (Bloch
820 & Sacks, 2018). However, the adjacency and connection relations did not provide such unique
821 feature value sets for all classes. Thus, the main limitation of implementing this as a standalone
822 tool for classification is in developing comprehensive and sophisticated rule sets (Bloch &
823 Sacks, 2018; Utkucu & Sacks, 2023; Wu & Zhang, 2019).

824 In the ML tool, six candidate computational models were tested on 25 object geometry features
825 retrieved from the objects' exact geometry in triangular mesh format. The best performance
826 was shown with the random forest model, with 78.5% prediction accuracy and a 0.75 F1 score.
827 Similarly, Abualdenien & Borrmann (2022) adopted a random forest algorithm to predict the
828 Level of Geometry of BIM objects and achieved accuracy at 83% and an F1 score of 0.83.
829 Although their performance is better than in this study, their dataset only contains four classes,
830 while ours has 40 object classes. Here too, this tool is insufficiently accurate when used in
831 isolation, but complements the ensemble process with data that is not used by other tools.

832 DL obtained the best classification accuracy (88.9%), which surpasses the best ML model by a
833 significant margin of 10.4% and is close to the performance of the best ensemble model (EM4).
834 This demonstrates that 3D visual features embedded in 2D images are particularly useful for
835 3D object classification and can be effectively extracted by the deep learning mechanism. In
836 fact, the performance of the MVCNN algorithm could be improved if the images were rendered
837 in a higher resolution (so that more geometric details can be captured) and in colour. Compared
838 to other tools, DL is much more computationally expensive, requiring more time to train and
839 perform the inference even using a GPU. A promising solution is to devise a light-weight CNN
840 model that requires fewer images for training and inference.

841 Furthermore, we note that the DL tool encountered challenges in distinguishing objects with
842 similar visual shapes (notably in the *IfcDuctSegment_Round* and *IfcPipeSegment* classes
843 discussed in Section 6 and shown in Figures 3 and 4). This issue was mitigated by amalgamating
844 3D object geometry features (ML) with object visual features (DL). The overall improvement
845 attained by integrating semantic, spatial topology, and geometry features with the visual
846 features amounted to +2.1% when comparing the DL tool's standalone prediction performance
847 to that of EM4.

848 **7.3. Ensemble Model Performance**

849 Eight EMs were established by testing the different integration combinations of the individual
850 tools. The best performance (91.0% prediction accuracy, 91.8% precision, 87.3% recall, and
851 0.88 F1 score) was achieved with the integration of four tools. When comparing EM4 to the

852 standalone learning models (ML with 78.5% prediction accuracy and DL with 88.9% prediction
853 accuracy), the prediction accuracy was raised respectively by +12.5% and +1.1%. T tests
854 showed that these differences are significant. In the literature, Yu et al. (2023) also implemented
855 ensemble learning for the BIM object classification in nine classes and enhanced the predicted
856 class accuracy in their model by +5.0%. Both our experiments and a prior study conducted by
857 Yu et al. (2023) indicate that ensemble learning can be an effective learning approach for the
858 BIM object classification task.

859 To sum up, the outcomes of this study show that the ensemble learning approach effectively
860 combines the advantages of individual tools and overcomes the weaknesses of individual tools,
861 notwithstanding the particularly strong performance of the DL tool. The ensemble learning
862 approach indicated that different and various object features in heterogeneous data sources can
863 be integrated via a multi-learning model. In addition, semantic and symbolic information about
864 the BIM object and relationships were used together.

865 **7.4 Limitations**

866 Constructing a dataset to encompass sufficiently wide-ranging samples, evenly distributed
867 across classes, while also constructing an adequately extensive training dataset, is challenging
868 (Bloch & Sacks, 2018; Koo et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2022). In the presence of heterogeneous
869 geometric variations within a given class, the classification model may encounter challenges in
870 effectively accommodating this diversity. Therefore, the consideration of finely-grained object
871 levels incorporating sub-classes might be needed (Collins, 2021). Although the developed BIM
872 object dataset compiles a broad set of BIM objects within the context of building performance,
873 it is limited due to exclusion of structural elements and some MEP objects (e.g., flow storage
874 and treatment devices). Consequently, the potential exists to enhance the dataset by
875 incorporating additional BIM object classes.

876 The semantic and topology information of the objects is easily accessible for the classification
877 task, but they are not sufficient for robust classification, as indicated by the poor results of EM2.
878 Therefore, this information was used to supplement the object features within the scope of the
879 learning approach, although, contrary to expectations, the contribution of these features was
880 relatively small. The learning-oriented approaches (ML with random forest and DL with
881 MVCNN) exhibit more powerful prediction performance than algorithm-based tools (SKS and
882 RBI) when handling comprehensive and complicated datasets. This is a similar result to that of
883 Bloch & Sacks (2018), where an ML approach achieved superior performance in classifying a
884 building's spaces than a rule-based algorithm. In this study, the reasons for this situation are: (i)
885 the dependency of the SKS approach on semantic information in objects' alphanumeric
886 properties, which are frequently absent or inaccurately specified; and (ii) the lack of
887 discriminating feature values for adjacency and connection relationships in the RBI tool. All

888 individual tools can be improved to some degree; however, developing an effective rule-based
889 system requires unique feature value combinations for every class, and this is difficult to
890 achieve when the number of classes is large (Bloch & Sacks, 2018; Utkucu & Sacks, 2023; Wu
891 & Zhang, 2019).

892 A final limitation is that validation was executed solely on the dataset, and not on case study
893 building models. The comparative prediction performance of EMs against a DL tool on a typical
894 building model, as would be encountered in engineering practice, is yet unknown. In ongoing
895 work, we are exploring a set of practical case studies, and we have made the dataset available
896 for other researchers to do the same.

897 **8. CONCLUSIONS**

898 The utility of BIM models for building performance simulation and analysis performance tasks
899 is hampered by challenges in extracting and pre-processing information from BIM models. The
900 challenges arise from several factors: insufficient levels of classification detail, discrepancies
901 between the BIM model schema and the native schema of building performance software,
902 inconsistencies in data export functions, and errors stemming from inadequate modelling
903 practices. These obstacles collectively impede the seamless integration of BIM data into
904 building performance analyses and simulations. Researchers have long sought solutions to such
905 interoperability problems, and some have argued that semantic enrichment based on automated
906 classification can greatly improve the utility of BIM models. To date, most state-of-the-art BIM
907 object classification methods have applied a single technique with some subset of object
908 features (e.g., geometry and spatial topology). However, building performance analyses require
909 a diverse range of objects encompassing various aspects of a building and its systems. These
910 objects include architectural, structural, and MEP elements and they have diverse shapes and
911 properties, posing a challenge for accurate and consistent identification using any single AI tool.

912 This study designed, implemented and tested four classification tools and a variety of ensemble
913 learning models for automated classification of performance domain building elements in BIM
914 models. The four tools use different object features and different methods: (i) SKS for BIM
915 objects' alphanumeric properties; (ii) RBI for adjacency and connection relationships among
916 the BIM objects; (iii) ML using 25 object geometry features; (iv) DL using visual shape features
917 in 2D images rendered from the BIM objects. The results show that the ensemble learning
918 approach is a promising way to combine the strengths of different techniques: with limited
919 effort to perfect the system, the EM model that incorporated four tools achieved classification
920 accuracy of 91.0% and an F1 score of 0.88. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt
921 to integrate a range of methods and data sources for classification of the rich variety of BIM
922 objects in the performance domain. Not only is the approach novel, it also yields better results

923 and more fine-grained classifications than other approaches reported to date.

924 This result increases confidence in the prospect of success in developing generic semantic
925 enrichment tools for preparing useful BIM models for performance analysis from standard,
926 imperfect BIM models. Such enrichment tools can be tailored to the specific needs of the
927 receiving applications with no dependence on or knowledge of the source modelling software.
928 Such tools are also essential for the function of intelligent cloud BIM systems (Sacks et al.,
929 2022).

930 The performance domain BIM object dataset compiled and published in the context of this work
931 is also a significant contribution to future research and development, as none of the few existing
932 open-source object datasets have fine-grained object classes (greater classification detail than
933 the standard IFC schema defines) with a broad set of object samples. The dataset contains 3,410
934 furnishing and MEP objects at a minimum LOD 300, each with IFC, PLY geometry, and 2D
935 image files. The objects are roughly evenly distributed across 40 object classes: seven
936 furnishing classes and 33 MEP classes. These classes are relevant for performance analyses
937 such as energy efficiency (e.g., fans, pumps, thermostats, radiators, and HVAC distribution
938 system components such as diffusers, and duct fittings and segments), visual quality (e.g.,
939 switches, sockets, lighting fixtures, and furniture objects as a target illuminance level measure),
940 acoustics (e.g., alarms), water supply (e.g., system distribution objects like pipe fittings and
941 segments), and fire protection (e.g., sprinklers and sensors). The dataset can serve as a
942 benchmark for the development of BIM object classification tools and techniques.

943 The research was limited to the building performance domain, but should be equally applicable
944 to any functional analysis that requires specifically tailored input from generic BIM models.
945 Moreover, the validation process was confined to the dataset – the tools have yet to be tested
946 with typical building models. Substantial testing on typical BIM models from industry is needed
947 to establish the effectiveness of the approach in production settings.

948 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

949 The structured BIM object dataset, ensemble models, and developed algorithms can be
950 retrieved from a GitHub repository. Currently, the BIM object dataset is available via this link:
951 <https://github.com/duyguutkucu/BIMObjectDataset/tree/main>

952 **DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST**

953 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
954 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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1208 APPENDICES

1209 Appendix A. Keyword Sets Corresponding to the Object Classes

Class No.	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Keyword Set
1				Bed	{FURNISHING, FURNITURE, BED}
2				Cabinet	{FURNISHING, FURNITURE, CABINET}
3				Chair	{FURNISHING, FURNITURE, CHAIR, SEAT}
4	<i>IfcFurnishingElement</i>	<i>IfcFurniture</i>	-	Desk	{FURNISHING, FURNITURE, DESK}
5				Shelf	{FURNISHING, FURNITURE, SHELF}
6				Sofa	{FURNISHING, FURNITURE, SOFA, SALON, LOUNGE}
7				Table	{FURNISHING, FURNITURE, TABLE, KITCHEN, DINING}
8	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcAirTerminal</i>	Diffuser	{FLOW, AIR, TERMINAL, DIFFUSER, HVAC}
9	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowController</i>	<i>IfcAirTerminalBox</i>	VAV	{FLOW, CONTROL, AIR, TERMINAL, BOX, VAV, HVAC}
10	<i>IfcDistributionControlElement</i>	<i>IfcAlarm</i>		Alarm	{CONTROL, ALARM}
11				Camera	{FLOW, TERMINAL, AUDIO, VISUAL, APPLIANCE, CAMERA, VIDEO}
12	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcAudioVisualAppliance</i>	Speaker	{FLOW, TERMINAL, AUDIO, VISUAL, APPLIANCE, SPEAKER}
13				Television (TV)	{FLOW, TERMINAL, AUDIO, VISUAL, APPLIANCE, TELEVISION, TV}
14	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowFitting</i>	<i>IfcCableCarrierFitting</i>	Cable Carrier Fitting	{FLOW, FITTING, CABLE, CARRIER, CONDUIT, ELECTRIC}

15	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowSegment</i>	<i>IfcCableCarrierSegment</i>	Cable Carrier Segment	{FLOW, SEGMENT, CABLE, CARRIER, CONDUIT, ELECTRIC}
16				Bend	{FLOW, FITTING, DUCT, BEND, ELBOW, HVAC, VENTILATION}
17	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowFitting</i>	<i>IfcDuctFitting</i>	Junction	{FLOW, FITTING, DUCT, JUNCTION, HVAC, VENTILATION}
18				Transition	{FLOW, FITTING, DUCT, TRANSITION, HVAC, VENTILATION}
19	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowSegment</i>	<i>IfcDuctSegment</i>	Rectangular	{FLOW, SEGMENT, DUCT, RECTANGULAR, HVAC, VENTILATION}
20				Round	{FLOW, SEGMENT, DUCT, ROUND, HVAC, VENTILATION}
21	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcElectricAppliance</i>	Cooker	{FLOW, TERMINAL, ELECTRIC, APPLIANCE, COOK, OVEN, KITCHEN}
22				Refrigerator	{FLOW, TERMINAL, ELECTRIC, APPLIANCE, REFRIGERATOR, FREEZER, KITCHEN}
23	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowMovingDevice</i>	<i>IfcFan</i>	Fan	{FLOW, MOVING, FAN, AIR}
24	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcFireSuppressionTerminal</i>	Fire Extinguisher	{FLOW, TERMINAL, FIRE, EXTINGUISHER}
25				Sprinkler	{FLOW, TERMINAL, FIRE, SPRINKLER}
26	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcLightFixture</i>	Light Fixture	{FLOW, TERMINAL, LIGHT, FIXTURE, LAMP, BULB}
27	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcOutlet</i>	Socket	{FLOW, TERMINAL, OUTLET, SOCKET, PLUG, ELECTRIC}
28				Bend	{FLOW, FITTING, PIPE, BEND, ELBOW, WATER}
29	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowFitting</i>	<i>IfcPipeFitting</i>	Junction (Lateral)	{FLOW, FITTING, PIPE, JUNCTION, LATERAL, WATER}
30				Junction (Tee)	{FLOW, FITTING, PIPE, JUNCTION, TEE, WATER}
31				Transition	{FLOW, FITTING, PIPE, TRANSITION, WATER}
32	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowSegment</i>	<i>IfcPipeSegment</i>	Pipe Segment	{FLOW, SEGMENT, PIPE, WATER, SEWAGE}

33	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowMovingDevice</i>	<i>IfcPump</i>	Pump	{FLOW, MOVING, PUMP, WATER}
34	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcSanitaryTerminal</i>	Sink	{FLOW, TERMINAL, SANITARY, SINK, BATHROOM}
35				Toilet	{FLOW, TERMINAL, SANITARY, TOILET, BATHROOM, WC, SEWAGE}
36	<i>IfcDistributionControlElement</i>	<i>IfcSensor</i>	-	Sensor	{CONTROL, SENSOR}
37	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowTerminal</i>	<i>IfcSpaceHeater</i>	Radiator	{FLOW, TERMINAL, SPACE, HEATER, RADIATOR}
38	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowController</i>	<i>IfcSwitchingDevice</i>	Switch	{FLOW, CONTROL, SWITCH}
39	<i>IfcDistributionControlElement</i>	<i>IfcUnitaryControlElement</i>	-	Thermostat	{CONTROL, UNITARY, THERMOSTAT}
40	<i>IfcDistributionFlowElement</i>	<i>IfcFlowController</i>	<i>IfcValve</i>	Valve	{FLOW, CONTROL, VALVE, WATER}

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